

**FORECAST OF THE AVERAGE ANNUAL INFLOW OF AMUDARYA
RIVER WATER RESOURCE**

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Abstract:

In this article, we have analyzed the change in the Amudarya River, on the basis of historical long-term statistical data, using ARIMA and the Exponential Smoothing Approach.

Keywords: Aral Sea, Amu Darya, water resource, forecast, ARIMA.

Introduction:

This study has attempted to assess the impact of the Aral Sea disaster on global processes in the atmosphere. Until 1960, the Aral Sea was the fourth largest inland lake in the world. Located in the heart of the Central Asian deserts, at an altitude of 53 meters above sea level, the Aral Sea served as the giant evaporator [1]. As the Aral Sea is located on the route of a powerful jet airstream from west to east, this moist flow has moved along the whole Central Asian region, softening the climate of the region, to the Pamir mountain ranges. There, part of the air currents surrounds the Pamir Mountains from the north and moves further to the east, and the other is retained by mountains and falls as precipitation. Further, the water would return to the Aral Sea through rivers Amu Darya and Syr Darya.

Today, the Aral Sea and its surrounding areas have become world-famous as a result of man-made environmental disaster. With increasing water consumption associated with the development of new irrigated areas, the increase in population, the influx of water into the sea from the two major river systems in the basin - the Amu Darya and Syr Darya has almost completely stopped.

Method:

Fluctuation of annual river runoff and its distribution in a year: To characterize variability of annual runoff in the practice of hydrological calculations, methods of mathematical statistics, in particular, distribution and supply curves, are widely used.

Smoothing and extrapolation of curves to specified security limits is carried out analytically using some typical equations. In the practice of hydrological calculations, the normal, log normal, binomial asymmetric curve and the Pearson III type distribution curve are more often used. The parameters of the theoretical security curve are: the first arithmetic mean of the series, the second coefficient of variability, or variations, the annual runoff, the third coefficient of annual flow asymmetry. Annual flow rates relative to its rate.

Probabilistic distribution used in hydrology. Since hydrological phenomena are characterized by considerable variability, randomness and uncertainty, it should be recognized that the statistical analysis of hydrological data does not always give the right result. The sources of the uncertainty of the repeatability analysis may be the representativeness of the analytical approach, the choice of the probability distribution, and the method of estimating the parameters.

Probabilistic distribution is used in many hydrological studies, for example, in the study of extremely high and extremely low runoff, droughts, reservoir volumes, rainfall, and time series modeling.

The normal distribution is probably the most popular statistical distribution. It is also known as the Gaussian distribution or error function. Many statistical parameters are found to be approximately normally distributed; therefore, the normal distribution is

often used for statistical inferences. A variety of natural phenomena either approximately follow a normal distribution or can be transformed to follow a normal distribution. Hazen (1914), who introduced the normal probability paper for an analysis of hydrologic data, made one of the earliest applications of the normal distribution in hydrology. Markovic (1965) fitted the normal distribution to annual rainfall and runoff data. Slack et al. (1975) showed that when the information about the distribution of floods and economic losses associated with the design of flood retardation structures was lacking, it was better to use the normal distribution than other distributions such as extreme value, lognormal, Weibull, etc. The other advantages of the normal distribution are that it is extensively tabulated and the standardized normal variate is the same as the frequency factor.

A random variable X is defined to have a normal distribution if its probability density

$$f_x(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_x^2}} \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{x - \mu_x}{\sigma_x} \right)^2 \right]$$

function is given by

satisfying $-\infty < x < +\infty$ and $\sigma^2 > 0$. Here μ_x and σ_x^2 are parameters which turn out to be the mean and standard deviation of the distribution.

ARIMA: Creation of the ARIMA model for prediction of dynamics of time series: The ARIMA models are under construction on the basis of background of the studied time series. This model was for the first time offered by J. Boks and G. Jenkins and therefore in some sources the model of an autoregression of the integrated sliding average is also called "Isolation ward Jenkins model" or in English-speaking literature of Auto Regressive Integrated Moving Average model (ARIMA-model). The ARIMA model represents generalization of model of the autoregression sliding average and is intended for the description of nonstationary time series $Y_t, t = \overline{1, T}$.

In the General case, the model is as follows:

ARIMA(p, d, q), here

- p – autoregression order;
- d – integration order;
- q – order of moving average.

Creation of the AR model and the MA model assumes a stationarity of time series. The stationarity in time series means that the relative probability distribution of m of observations of a number of Y_t does not depend on t time. As reception of overcoming a problem of not stationarity of a time series it is possible to use transition to a number of increments:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta^1 Y_t &= Y_t - Y_{t-1} \\ \Delta^2 Y_t &= \Delta Y_t - Y_{t-1} \\ &\dots \\ \Delta^d Y_t &= \Delta^{d-1} Y_t - \Delta^{d-1} Y_{t-1} \sim ARIMA(p, q) \Rightarrow Y_t \sim ARIMA(p, d, q) \end{aligned}$$

If a number of increments of an order of d is stationary $\Delta^d Y_t$, then the initial time series of Y_t is called d . integrated an order.

The quantity of differences which undertake for achievement of a stationarity, is defined by d . difference order. The necessary order of a difference is defined by a research of the schedule of a row. The strong changes of level (the strong jumps up or down) usually demand capture of a nonseasonal difference of first order. The strong changes of an inclination demand capture of a difference of the second order.

Exponential Smoothing Approach: Exponential smoothing techniques are widely used for the time series analysis because of their simplicity and robustness as automatic forecasting procedures (CorberánVallet et al. 2011). Referring to Bowerman et al. (2005), the exponential smoothing approach can be effectively used to forecast stochastic time series. It constructs a time trend forecast with the ability to easily adjust for past errors and prepare follow-on forecasts. Single, double, and triple exponential smoothing techniques are available depending on whether no linear or quadratic trend is specified. Among different approaches, the Holt's Linear Exponential Smoothing Technique is used to handle non-seasonal series by introducing smoothing parameters (Oyatoye and Fabson 2011).

Holt's method is also known as Holt-Winters double exponential smoothing technique, originally presented by Charles C. Holt and Peter Winters (Gelper et al., 2007). It uses two smoothing parameter and is good in handling trends. This method

is much like SEST excludes the two components which are level and trend estimate that must be updated on each period. The level is a smoothed estimate of the value of the data at the end of each period while trend is smoothed estimate of average growth at the end of each period (Kalekar, 2004). Holt's method requires three equations:

the level estimate:

$$S_t = \alpha y_t + (1 - \alpha)(S_{t-1} + T_{t-1})$$

the trend estimate:

$$T_t = \beta(S_t - S_{t-1}) + (1 - \beta)T_{t-1}$$

forecast m period in the future:

$$f_{t+m} = \alpha_t + b_t * m$$

where y_t is the actual value for period t , α and β is the value of the smoothing parameter, and T_{t-1} is the prediction value for period $t + 1$ while T_t is the forecast value for period t .

Results

Average annual distribution of runoff to the Amu Darya rivers: The analysis was carried out based on data on average monthly and average annual water discharge of the Amu Darya, data on average monthly and mean annual air temperatures, monthly and annual precipitation. Methods of statistical analysis are used in the work. Trends were calculated by the method of least squares, cyclicity was estimated by constructing integral difference curves. The tightness of the connection between the analyzed series was estimated using correlation analysis. The reliability of linear trends and correlation coefficients was estimated at 95% significance level.

To calculate the annual distribution of river flow, this method determines the intra-seasonal distribution of the runoff. Due to the fact that the annual distribution of runoff depends on the water content of the season, the calculation was made for

different water groups - high, medium and low water with an equal number of years in each group.

The duration and boundaries of hydrological seasons are as follows: spring (March-May), summer-autumn (June-November), winter (December-February). The limiting period of the year and season are chosen based on the prevailing type of water consumption and the relative water content of the season. For the limiting period, a low water season (both low-water seasons: summer-autumn and winter) is taken, and winter is the limiting season. The obtained results show that the main part of the river flow takes place in the spring season, and the smallest in the winter season. The results of the calculations are given in Tab.1.

Provision of the year, %	Spring				Summer-autumn							Winter				Amount for the year, %
	III	IV	V	Sum %	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	Sum %	XII	I	II	Sum %	
25	4.0	4.7	10.8	19.5	13.0	15.1	11.1	12.6	9.2	4.4	65.5	5.5	5.2	4.3	15.0	100
50	2.6	2.8	10.9	16.3	16.1	19.5	14.2	10.8	7.4	5.3	73.2	3.6	4.0	2.9	10.5	100
75	1.4	4.8	10.3	16.5	17.2	21.1	15.3	10.4	6.3	4.2	74.5	3.8	2.9	2.3	9.0	100

Table 1. The annual distribution of the Amu Darya river flow in the last 57 years (part of the territory of Aral region) for years of different provision (as a percentage of annual runoff)

According to the distribution of the Amu Darya, the share of spring flow for the high water group is 19.5%, medium-water - 16.3%, low-water - 16.5% of the annual runoff, and for winter runoff - 15% for the high-water group, 10.5% for Medium water and 9% for low-water. In the summer-autumn season, a large water group accounts for 65.5%, for the middle-water group - 73.2%, for the shallow water group - 74.5% of the annual runoff.

The distribution of runoff by months within different seasons is not the same. The results of in-season distribution of runoff are given in Table 2.

Season water resource group %	Spring			Summer-autumn						Winter		
	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII	I	II
25	20.8	23.1	56.1	19.6	23.0	17.1	18.8	14.6	7.0	36.4	34.7	28.8
50	15.9	17.3	66.9	22.0	26.5	19.3	15.0	10.0	7.2	34.4	38.2	27.4
75	8.3	29.2	62.5	23.1	28.2	20.4	14.0	8.2	6.1	41.9	32.8	25.3
Average	15.0	23.2	61.8	21.6	25.9	18.9	15.9	11.0	6.8	37.6	35.2	27.2

Table 2. In-season distribution of runoff for different seasonal water groups (As a percentage of seasonal runoff)

The most uneven intra-seasonal distribution is characteristic for the spring period. The largest monthly runoff on the river. Amu Darya is observed in May and is 61.8%, and the smallest in March and equal to 15% of the spring. This is explained by intensive snowmelt in late March and early April. In the summer-autumn season, the distribution of the flow is more evenly distributed. The lowest monthly flow for the distribution of the Amu Darya is observed in November and is 11.1% of the seasonal one. The distribution of runoff within the summer-autumn season is characterized by a regular decrease in the monthly runoff from the beginning of the season to July-September and then by a gradual change at the end of the season. During this period, the rivers feed mostly underground waters, which are gradually depleted by July-September, and precipitation, which falls in large numbers during this season, does not participate in the feeding of rivers, as they are used for evaporation, soil wetting and infiltration. Then, by reducing evaporation and falling autumn rain, the monthly run-off increases by the end of the season.

In the winter season, the distribution of the flow of the rivers in question is different. For the distribution of the Amu-Darya typical flow distribution within the winter season is typical. The largest runoff is in December and is 37.6% of the winter runoff, and then the run-off is decreasing by February. The smallest average monthly flow in February is 27.2% of the seasonal. This pattern of distribution of runoff within the season is due to the gradual depletion of groundwater during the winter season. This type of distribution of flow is not typical for the rivers of the given region and is caused by planned discharges of the reservoir in winter. Figure 13

shows the normal distribution of the change in the runoff of the last 57 years to the northern part of the Amu Darya River.

As a result of studies of the intra-annual distribution of the flow of right-bank tributaries of the Amu Darya River (within the Republic of Karakalpakstan), updated data on the distribution of river runoff were obtained in comparison with the data presented. The revealed changes in the intra-annual distribution of runoff are due to the lengthening of the series of actual observations and the resulting changes in runoff under the influence of climatic and anthropogenic factors.

Forecast of the average annual inflow based on the method of ARIMA and Exponential smoothing

In this part in the paper, we study the runoff using a time series for hydrology stations in Samanbay in Karakalpakstan province in Uzbekistan by various statistical methods to enable us to analyse the behaviour of runoff in the study areas. The time-series analysis is an important tool in modelling and forecasting runoff. Two time series analysis techniques were applied in this study, the Holt-Winter's exponential smoothing and the Box-Jenkins' modeling method (ARIMA). Both models were found to be adequate for forecasting. Diagnostic checking confirms the adequacy of the models. The ARIMA (1, 0, 1)(1, 0, 1)₁₂ model give us information that can help use of water resources in Karakalpakstan Republic (in Uzbekistan). Time-series analysis is an important tool in modelling and forecasting runoff. The ARIMA and Holt-Winter models were built on the basis of exponential smoothing. All the models proved to be adequate. Therefore it is possible to give information that can help decision makers establish strategies for the proper planning of agriculture, drainage systems and other water resource applications in Karakalpakstan Republic. We obtained the best performance from forecasting with the ARIMA Model(1,0,1)(1,0,1). Many methods and approaches for formulating forecasting models are available in the literature. This paper deals exclusively with a time series-forecasting model, in particular, the Auto Regressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA). Box and Jenkins [1] described these models. The Box-Jenkins (ARIMA)

model has been successfully applied in various water and environmental management applications. Other successful automatic forecasting methods in practice are based on exponential smoothing models. There are a variety of such models, each having a property that provides forecasts which are weighted averages of past observations with recent observations given relatively more weight than older observations. The name “exponential smoothing” reflects the fact that the weights decrease exponentially as the observations get older (Hyndman [2]). Winter generalized the Holt exponential method to handle seasonality in time series data by introducing a third factor into time series analysis which is seasonal smoothing. Seasonal smoothing is an estimated value of seasonal growth rate reflecting the seasonal pattern of time series data [3]. Since the time series data for rainfall show a certain seasonality, the Holt-Winters Exponential Smoothing model is suitable for further investigation. We adapt two approaches in modeling and forecasting runoff in this part in the paper. The next section is the materials and methods based on the Box Jenkins model building technique and exponential smoothing methods.

Discussion: The historical runoff dataset is for Karakalpakstan province. The data was collected from Samanbay stations and it consists of 57 years of monthly data from 1960 to 2016. The Autocorrelation Function Plot of the annual decrement of runoff in Fig. 14 shows that runoff decrement has relatively low autocorrelations at lag levels of multiple 12, which are lags 12, 24, 36, and 48. This is evidence for the certain seasonality of runoff decrement dataset with the period of every year.

Fig 1. Autocorrelation and partial autocorrelation from Arima and Holt-Winters

Analysis of the results allows us to make the following conclusion: using ARIMA, a relatively accurate forecast of the average annual inflow rate for 2002-2016 was obtained. As it turned out, after 2017-2026 the forecast error was from -0.077 to 0.66. All predicted values fall within 95 percent confidence interval. Corresponds to the model, built on the basis of data for 2017-2026. The prediction error is 0.089.

Fig 2. Forecasting from method ARIMA and Holt-Winters

In order to improve predictability, seasonal models such as ARIMA(p,d,q)(P,D,Q) and Holt-Winter's model will be fitted to each dataset, then the fitted models will be used to make an out-of-sample forecast. The whole dataset from 1960 to 2016 is used as an example to illustrate the model fitting process. As shown in Fig. 15, the Residual and upper (lower) bound for the annual runoff data are not stable which supports the assumption that the series is changeable. It is clear that we have no observable pattern in the residual errors which shows that the model could be used to represent our data.

Forecasting year	Average annual runoff		Lower bound (95%)		Upper bound (95%)	
	ARIMA	Holt-Winter	ARIMA	Holt-Winter	ARIMA	Holt-Winter
2017	0.114	20.650	-1401.518	-903.889	1401.747	945.190
2018	0.093	11.606	-1401.882	-927.447	1402.068	950.659
2019	0.076	2.562	-1402.127	-951.029	1402.279	956.154
2020	0.062	-6.482	-1402.292	-974.638	1402.416	961.674
2021	0.051	-15.526	-1402.404	-998.272	1402.505	967.220
2022	0.041	-24.570	-1402.480	-1021.934	1402.563	972.794
2023	0.034	-33.614	-1402.533	-1045.625	1402.600	978.397
2024	0.027	-42.658	-1402.568	-1069.344	1402.623	984.028
2025	0.022	-51.702	-1402.593	-1093.093	1402.638	989.688
2026	0.018	-60.746	-1402.610	-1116.872	1402.647	995.380

Table 3. Compare results ARIMA and Holt-Winters

It is very likely that with the help of historical hydrological data, when the results of the forecast were compared (Table 6), an assessment was made that in the next 10 years the river water balance will steadily decrease. The forecast was carried out in comparison with the volume of water that was observed in 2002-2016. During these years, the river runoff coincided with the low-water period (4.6-227.9 m³/s), so the result of the forecast gives low indicators.

The ARIMA forecasting model does not always have the desired accuracy for a given range. In the forecast ranges, the uncertainty in the estimation of the parameters is not shown. Consequently, the intervals are narrower than they should be, preventing the addition of further uncertainty. In addition, ARIMA model has many assumptions that cannot be met. One of the most important assumptions is that the historical pattern of the data will not change during the forecast period. If the model assumptions are true, we obtain an excellent forecast, otherwise the results are not satisfactory.

The Holt-Winters model is simple and can provide accurate forecasting results as those obtained with more complex techniques. This method is popular, easy to use and generally works well in practical applications. However, it is recommended that the horizon of the predictions made with the Holt-Winters method does not exceed the seasonal cycle of the series, because the predictions with a larger horizon tend to have reduced accuracy. Given the limitations of this study, it is suggested as future

research, the comparison between natural computing based models, as well as the particle swarms techniques for optimization [8].

Other methods of forecasting. An opportunity prediction of inflow on a basis use of models of an autoregression and the sliding average of different orders was investigated; various options of prediction of inflow on the basis of selection of year analog, and also the alternate methods of the analysis these-neural network methods were applied. However it was not succeeded to receive satisfactory results in of accuracy of forecasts on the basis of these methods.

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